

Translation of Mahakavi Bharathi's Poem "Pennukku Arivurai"

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Advice to Woman

No need to show no need to pomp -tiny woman
Intellect is enough - tiny woman

Wife of lover - tiny woman
Eloped by another - tiny woman

So it is of fear - tiny woman
Do go here and there - tiny woman

If you find a guy with goggling eye - tiny woman
Don't see with your eye - tiny woman

If you see the lad going shop - tiny woman
Don't stare your eye - tiny woman

If you see a rogue - tiny woman
Don't play with your legs - tiny woman

Having the bindi on the forehead - tiny woman
Don't speak very closely - tiny woman

Having eyetex on your brow - tiny woman
Don't say a lie - tiny woman

Having earrings weared - tiny woman
Don't walk hip-hop - tiny woman

Chewing beetle leaves - tiny woman
Don't see a wanton boy - tiny woman

Chewing tobacco - tiny woman
Don't see a juvenile boy - tiny woman

Don't hire and speak - tiny woman
With the by walker - tiny woman

You don't sarcasm - tiny woman
On the mob going for market - tiny woman

On the road of Salukar - tiny woman
Don't put any fight - tiny woman

Don't do sarcasm on - tiny woman
The neighborly women - tiny woman

O the possessor of lean hip - tiny woman
Don't speak adamant - tiny woman

O' the head weight - tiny woman
Don't brawl - tiny woman

O' the wide headed - tiny woman
Don't speak of valour - tiny woman

O' the iron hearted - tiny woman
Don't do mischief - tiny woman

Don't be without dignity - tiny woman
Who have the long curling tress - tiny woman

Googling eye - tiny woman
Don't cheat - tiny woman

Beautiful lipped - tiny woman
Don't scold anybody - tiny woman

Parrot nosed - tiny woman
Don't tear anybody - tiny woman

Noble toothed - tiny woman
Don't beget any problem - tiny woman

Lean necked - tiny woman
Don't spread rumors - tiny woman

Translated- Mr.B.Thangamarimuthu